

ORGANIZATION OF THE PROCESS OF TRAINING SIMULTANEOUS INTERPRETERS

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ABSTRACT

This article is about the organization of the process of training simultaneous interpreters in our country and the requirements for them.

This article's thesis is dedicated to one of the urgent tasks in the system of higher and secondary special education of the Republic of Uzbekistan, as well as the importance of the components of the role of the educational system in organizing the process of training simultaneous translators and its features. The research is related to the analysis and comparison of effective methods of training simultaneous interpreters in Uzbekistan, such as mixed and complex methods of teaching English as a foreign language. Extra-university translation training plays an important role in Switzerland. Only in Geneva, the Graduate School of Translation is part of the university and is a member of CIUTI. Here the training lasts 4 years. Targeted translation training begins only in the third year. Interpretation is differentiated in training from written translation. Students master two foreign languages and are required to complete an internship abroad for each of them during one semester. Interpretation and translation training in the UK is carried out on special master's courses at five universities in England: Westminster, Bath, Salford, Bradford, Herriotthwaite. Since September 2001, the University of Leeds has opened its Master's program in Interpretation. A prerequisite for admission to the courses is sufficient language training. The proof is usually a bachelor's degree in foreign languages (philology). According to current trends, education is conducted mainly from a foreign language to the native one. The training takes 1 year and includes three trimesters. Within the 1st and 2nd trimester, 5-6 training modules are possible and, accordingly, specialization in either oral or written translation. Simultaneous interpretation and translation theory are taught from the second trimester. Starting from the last month of the 19th of the first trimester, students undergo training every two weeks as conference interpreters on typical topics. Translation has a long history. Its roots go back to these distant ones. The need for Humanity, where the main language began to break down

separately, distances knew languages and a number of languages began to appear, and linguist translators began to appear who had the opportunity to mediate between specific language communities. In the modern world, translation activities are becoming more and more widespread and have great social significance. The occupation translator appeared in public, and experienced translators began to multiply, in which separate educational institutions were created for teaching in many countries.

The results of the training of translators-synchronous translators, including on the basis of higher educational institutions, have encountered many obstacles. Synchronous translation activities have three characteristics:

1. Linguistic,
2. Temporary
3. Psychological.

The linguistic nature of the activity of a synchronous translator depends on both. The linguistic differences between a particular language pair and one or the other are the methods that translators use to convey their original information without distorting it. A temporary characteristic of synchronous translation activity includes:

- simultaneous implementation of cognitive operations of understanding the source
- verbalization of the text and translation option in the target language.
- at the same time timetime, analysis of incoming information and selection of the translation option.

It is carried out in parallel with the above-mentioned operations. In this regard, the time factor is a determining feature of translation activity in simultaneous implementation. One of the psychological characteristics of a synchronous translator is the essential parameters of the professional reliability of a translator-synchronous translator.

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